

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10938764>

DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL SPHERES IN THE CITIES OF KASHKADARYA REGION

Safarov I.B

Teacher of Karshi State University

Rasulov F.I

A student of Karshi State University

Abstract: *In this article, the level of development of social spheres in the cities of Kashkadarya region is studied and analyzed. Proposals and recommendations on the development of social spheres in the cities of Kashkadarya region have been developed.*

Key words: *region, city, village, social, sectors, center, services.*

РАЗВИТИЕ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ СФЕРЫ В ГОРОДАХ КАШКАДАРЬИНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

Аннотация: *В данной статье изучен и проанализирован уровень развития социальной сферы в городах Кашкадарьинской области. Разработаны предложения и рекомендации по развитию социальной сферы в городах Кашкадарьинской области.*

Ключевые слова: *регион, город, село, социальная сфера, сектор, центр, услуги.*

When analyzing the social factors of the development of cities, first of all, it is necessary to determine the aspects that serve them and create (organize) the city. Therefore, in this work, not social spheres in general, but those that serve the population and their city-forming features are taken into account. Sectors that directly serve the population of existing cities have little influence on the formation of the wider socio-geographical environment. Therefore, from the point of view of urbanization, it is not the industries that serve the city, but the influence of these industries outside the city that is of great importance. From a scientific point of view, the ideas of D. J. Friedman's "Center-periphery", T. Hegerstrand's "Diffusion of news", and V. Kristaller's "Central place" are of great methodological importance.

The German scientist V. Kristaller developed his idea of "Central Places", unlike the ideas of his compatriots I. Tunen and A. Weber, precisely within the framework of social spheres. The essence of V. Kristaller's scientific concept is the staggered placement of the areas of service to the population depending on the size of the settlements. In this respect, the hierarchical system of cities serves as the main concept in this idea. In this case, their centrality, the implementation of goods and services for the surrounding area, the existence of surrounding areas receiving them, and settlements of different sizes, that is, the distance between service centers and the area receiving them, the radius and ease of distribution of goods are the main content.

According to estimates, in the conditions of Uzbekistan, there is one rural medical center (QVP) for every 3 or 4 rural settlements. It almost corresponds to the level of the village assembly in the administrative-territorial division. The next step is the district center, which, depending on the demographic capacity of the place, takes QFY and QVP into its sphere of influence. The scope of service of the district or inter-district and regional centers will also expand in this order.

In Kashkadarya region, according to the above, the following can be distinguished:

- I. The regional center is the city of Karshi;
- II. Inter-district or district centers - the cities of Karshi, Shakhrisabz, Guzor;
- III. 14 cities and towns that function as district centers;
- IV. 148 QFY centers;
- V. 1046 rural settlements.

Areas of public service - trade, education, health care system are located in settlements, that is, in central places, at different levels. Each of these places has its own unique influence and scope of service. In this regard, cities are considered to be the center of the complex of social spheres of the region, in addition to performing the specific administrative (provincial and district centers) and economic (major industrial production facilities, transport hubs) "capital". Compared to rural areas, cities have a number of advantages in the placement of social and household service facilities due to the number of inhabitants, its high level of incorporation and employment, the fact that houses are built on a planned basis, and are well provided with transport and utility networks. Most of the cities of the South Uzbekistan region also serve as administrative centers of rural districts. This situation requires that the upper level of all social sphere facilities be located in cities and serve the population of the entire district. For this reason, proportionally increasing the number and quality of social infrastructure networks in cities plays an important role in ensuring the socio-economic well-being of regions.

It is known that the network and system of regional cities is not well developed, and their economic basis is not very strong. If direct economic functions are considered in this regard, it is possible to point out industrial centers such as Karshi, Mubarak, Shahrisabz, resource town Nuristan, and Guzor as a transport center. At the same time, most cities and towns function as regional centers. This, in turn, provides services to the residents of the district in accordance with their district-forming potential. In particular, the urban and rural population of the region is growing faster than in other regions of the republic. The increase in the number of the population, including its young population, requires wider development of social spheres in urban areas. In addition, the implementation of all the activities specified in the State Program "Year of Rural Development and Welfare" will impose new tasks on the cities and towns, which are the socio-economic centers of the regions.

Education, health care, retail trade and paid services play a leading role among the sectors of public service. Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya regions are not significantly different from other regions of our republic according to the level of development of social spheres, but at the same time they have a number of unique characteristics.

At the moment, the state's contribution to social spheres such as education, health, science and art in urban areas is large, and the provision of transport, communal and household services, trade and general catering, tourism and recreation to urban residents. sectors are almost entirely owned by the private sector.

Paid services. This sector includes passenger transportation, housing and communal services, communication, household, cultural, tourism and excursion, physical education and sports, sanatorium-resort and health services that directly serve the population. receives legal, banking and other services. For this reason, the good formation of this network determines the social development of cities. The increase in the volume of paid services, while bringing high income to the local budget, also has a positive effect on the employment of the city population.

The volume of paid services in Kashkadarya region in recent years has seen significant changes in the composition of this sector, the volume of communication, paid medicine and education, legal assistance, banking and insurance services has increased; Although the share of traditional passenger transportation, housing and communal services, household, cultural, tourism and excursion, sanatorium-resort and wellness services has decreased, the main part of paid services still belongs to these sectors. is coming In particular, more than 50 percent of the volume of paid services of the region in 2018 was attributed to the contribution of communal, construction, transport and financial services. Due to the rapid development of mobile

communication and Internet services, its share in paid services was equal to 9.1 percent, while other sectors made up a total of 35.8 percent.

The market of paid services in the region is divided differently not only in terms of content, but also by region. Districts and cities with a large demographic potential and a high level of urbanization received the bulk of the volume of paid services.

Also, the geography and volume of services will be high in areas with dense population and well-structured social infrastructure networks. In turn, the expansion of the type and volume of paid services serves as a leading factor in the increase of the employment level and real income of the population in the regions, the improvement of living conditions, as a result, the creation of an urban environment in the villages and the development of new towns.

Retail. Retail trade includes the sale of food, alcohol, non-food products, as well as catering establishments. As in the entire republic, in the Southern region, the needs of the population for the above products are mainly met by urban settlements, and accordingly, the main part of the district's retail trade volume is the markets, shops, public catering located in the cities and towns, which are the district and QFY centers. formed at the expense of enterprises. The economic geographical position of the cities (the main "central places"), their function, the population and the level of transport communications are important for the location of retail trade enterprises.

According to the results of 2022, 8851.4 bln. Soum retail service is provided. From the statistical data, we can see that 1/4 of the retail trade volume belongs to the share of the city of Karshi alone. Due to the convenience of economic geographical location, these cities have large and specialized (automotive and spare parts, farm and construction materials, livestock, clothing, agricultural products and wholesale) markets, which practically cover the entire region. serves the population.

The small share of Kasbi, Mirishkor, Nishon, Karshi, Koson and Mubarak districts in retail trade compared to the total population of the region is explained by the fact that the population's demand for many products is met at the expense of the city of Karshi. Shahrizabz city in Shahrizabz-Kitab group districts performs the same task. Also, there are large public catering establishments (restaurants, wedding halls, teahouses, cafes) in these cities and in the city centers where international highways pass.

The city of Karshi and the districts of Mubarak, Kitab, Koson, Yakkabog and Shahrizabz Angor with a high level of urbanization are the leaders in terms of average retail sales per capita. The index of retail trade per capita is much higher in the oasis only in the city of Karshi, and in all other districts it is less than 1,000. The retail trade index is especially low in Kasbi, Chirakchi, Karshi and Mirishkor districts. This is due

to the proximity of these districts to the administrative center of the region and the use of their markets.

In general, the development of social spheres in the region is inextricably linked with the processes of urbanization, and their upper echelons and main centers are located in urban areas. In this regard, the regional center - Karshi is on the first stage, Shahrisabz is on the second stage, the centers of rural districts are on the third stage, the centers of QFY are on the fourth stage, and the last, i.e., rural settlements are on the fifth stage. All of them together determine the system of territorial organization of social spheres in the region.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullayev O. Mintaqalar va mamlakatlar iqtisodiyoti. – T.: Yangi asr avlodi, 2009. – 282
2. Asanov G.R. Sotsial – iqtisodiy geografiya: termin va tushunchalar izohli lug‘ati. – T.: O‘qituvchi, 1990. – 248 b.
3. Ata–Mirzayev O.B. Regionalnoye prognozirovaniye rasseleniya i upravleniye protsessom urbanizatsii. – T.: Fan, 1979. – 92 s.
4. Soliyev A.S. Shaharlar geografiyasi. Ma’ruzalar matni – T.: O‘zMU, 2000.
5. Курбонов П.П. Жанубий Ўзбекистонда урбанизация жараёнлари. Монография. -Т.: «MUMTOZ SO`Z». 2019 йил. – 180 б.
6. Qurbonov P. Kichik shaharlarda agrosanoat majmuini rivojlanish imkoniyatlari va istiqbollari (Qashqadaryo viloyati misolida) //Nashrlar. – 2023. – С. 298-301.
7. Abdiholiqova G.A. Qashqadaryo viloyatida urbanizatsiya jarayonlari rivojlanishining iqtisodiy geografik jihatlari. Magistrlik dissertatsiya. 2022.
8. Safarov I. B. Geographical features of pilgrimage tourism (in the case of Kashkadarya region) //Экономика и социум. – 2023. – №. 2 (105). – С. 321-324.
9. Safarov I. B., Rasulov F. I. Prospects for the development of pilgrimage tourism (on the example of Koson district) //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 189-191.
10. Safarov I. B., Toshquvvatov I. T. Recreational and touristic opportunities of Uzbekistan’s mountains // Экономика и социум. – 2023. – №.11(114). – С. 303-312.
11. Сафаров И. Б., Халилов Н. Х. Экономико-географические проблемы градостроительства верхне-Кашкадарьинской области //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 707-713.
12. Safarov I. B., Omonullayev O. H. Hazrati Bashir qishlog‘ining ziyorat turizimi //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 4 SPECIAL. – С. 193-196.

13. Сафаров И. Б., Расулов Ф. И. Социально-экономические проблемы и перспективы развития городов Кашкадарьинской области // Экономика и социум. – 2024. . – №. 1 (116). – С. 1304-1311
14. Safarov I.B., Chorshamiev R.R. G`uzor tumani ziyoratgohlar maskani // Экономика и социум. – 2024. – №. 2 (117). – С. 609-616
15. Safarov I., Toshquvatov I. Organization of mountain tourism in Kashkadarya region and its significance //Евразийский журнал математической теории и компьютерных наук. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 3. – С. 7-12.
16. Safarov I. B., Chorshamiyev R. R., To`laganov N. U. Tohir va Zuhra ziyoratgohini geografik joylashuvi //Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования. – 2024. – Т. 15. – №. 3. – С. 3-6.
17. Qurbonov P. O`zbekistonda urbanizatsiya jarayonlari rivojlanishining asosiy bosqichlari //Scientific journal of the Fergana State University. – 2023. – №. 3. – С. 165-165.